

MORAL ISSUES IN THE WORKS OF CENTRAL ASIAN THINKERS (IX–XII CENTURIES)

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the moral views of Central Asian thinkers who lived and worked during the IX–XII centuries. The study focuses on prominent scholars such as Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Raykhon Beruni, and Yusuf Khajib, examining their reflections on morality, ethics, and human perfection, as well as the social impact of their ideas. The article also pays special attention to the connection between Islamic ethics and philosophy, highlighting their intellectual legacy.*

Keywords: *moral values; ethical heritage; spiritual maturity; spiritual legacy; patriotism; personal perfection; Central Asian moral thought; social ethics; humanism; contemporary values.*

Introduction

It is well known that high moral values serve as the foundation of any society's development and reflect its level of spiritual maturity. Accordingly, in the context of building the “Democratic Legal State and Civil Society” in Uzbekistan—the “Uzbek model”—special attention is paid to the moral and intellectual development of young people. As emphasized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “*If our youth possess high moral education, patriotism, and spiritual purity, no external threats can mislead us*” [1].

These considerations not only serve as guidance for raising today's generation but also highlight the importance of deeply studying our historical spiritual heritage, passed down from generation to generation. In particular, the intellectual environment of Central Asia in the IX–XII centuries—with its scholars, philosophers, and thinkers—represents a crucial period whose scientific and moral contributions retain enormous relevance today. During this era, the Muslim East, especially the region of Mawarannahr, witnessed a revival of science and spirituality that made a significant contribution to global civilization.

The thinkers of this period, including Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Abu Raykhon Beruni, and Yusuf Khajib, laid the foundations of scientific and moral development for subsequent generations. Their works addressed ethics not only from a religious perspective but also from social, philosophical, and humanistic viewpoints. This study aims to examine the ethical views of Central Asian thinkers of the IX–XII centuries, revealing their harmony with universal and contemporary values. Researching these works and integrating them into educational processes remains an urgent task.

Research Methods

The study employed methods including source analysis, objectivity, analysis and synthesis, comparison, creativity, historical approach, and logical reasoning.

Literature Review

Research on the ethical thought of Central Asia highlights the works of IX–XII century scholars as key sources. Their moral views are studied today in fields such as ethics, pedagogy,

philosophy, and religious studies. Al-Farabi, in his work “*Thoughts of the Virtuous Citizens*”, envisages building an ideal moral society. According to the scholar, the virtuous citizen must achieve spiritual perfection and be equipped with ethical virtues [2]. I. Sultonov evaluates Al-Farabi’s ethical ideas as follows: “*Al-Farabi was able to integrate ethics with politics, advancing the idea of a perfect state through the moral development of society*” [3].

Ibn Sina analyzed moral virtues not only in a religious context but also in medical and philosophical dimensions. In his *Canon of Medicine*, he identifies the cultivation of the soul, willpower, honesty, patience, and reflection as fundamental to human spiritual well-being [4,5]. Abu Raykhon Beruni emphasized moral integrity and truthfulness in scientific activity. In his works *India* and *Monuments of Ancient Peoples*, he promoted scientific honesty and impartiality as key principles [6,7]. Academician B. Gafurov described Beruni as a thinker who could harmonize knowledge with ethics, considering truth the highest value [8].

The work *Qutadghu Bilig* is regarded as a major example of Central Asian moral thought, portraying ethical relations between rulers, advisors, officials, and the people in poetic-philosophical language. A. Shoniyozov notes that Yusuf Khajib’s work represents the pinnacle of Turkic ethical-philosophical thought, remaining fully relevant to modern governance and social ethics [9,10]. The analysis of these thinkers demonstrates that IX–XII century ethics in Central Asia has immense importance for shaping contemporary moral consciousness. Their works provided practical guidance for implementing moral perfection in daily life, beyond mere religious instruction.

Research Results

As noted, high moral values serve as the foundation of any society’s development and reflect its level of spiritual maturity. These values contribute not only to the personal perfection of individuals but also to the stability, unity, and progress of the entire society. Experience from developed states demonstrates that material development cannot be sustainable without a corresponding moral and spiritual foundation.

From this perspective, the above analysis shows that Central Asian thinkers of the IX–XII centuries made a significant contribution to the development of ethical thought. Their ideas remain highly relevant today, particularly in addressing contemporary moral challenges. The table below presents a concise analysis of the ethical views of several prominent thinkers from Central Asia during the IX–XII centuries, highlighting their main works and contemporary significance:

Scholar	Works	Main Ethical Ideas	Contemporary Relevance
Abu Nasr Farabi	The Views of the Inhabitants of the Virtuous City	The concept of a virtuous individual and a virtuous society; political morality; wise and just leadership	Building a perfect society, ethical leadership, social justice
Abu Ali Ibn Sina	The Book of Knowledge (Donishnoma), Kitob ush-shifo (The Book of Healing)	Self-discipline, honesty, willpower, and spiritual purity	Personal perfection, psychological well-being, moral education
Abu Raykhon Beruni	Hindistan, Monuments from Ancient Peoples	Truthfulness, Scientific Integrity, Justice	Scientific Objectivity, Research Ethics, Fidelity to Facts

Scholar	Works	Main Ethical Ideas	Contemporary Relevance
Yusuf Khos Khajib	Qutadghu Bilig	Moral Responsibility Between Leader and People, Justice, Counsel, Patience	Ethics in State Governance, Culture of Service, Responsible Leadership

Research Results

This table presents how the ethical views of these thinkers were formed in different aspects and highlights their relevance today. It is evident that their works not only carry historical value but can also serve as practical guides for contemporary education, governance, social, and cultural spheres. Deep study and integration of these ideas into the upbringing of youth is one of the key directions for national development.

Ibn Sina (Avicenna) paid close attention to the classification of sciences in his era and authored the work *Aqşam al-Ulum al-Aqliya* (“Classification of the Rational Sciences”). In it, practical philosophy is divided into three parts—ethics, economics, and politics. The first part addresses the moral and behavioral conduct of an individual; the second concerns interpersonal relations within the family and household; and the third part explores broader social interactions. Each category is further subdivided into specialized branches. The text discusses 29 fields of knowledge and emphasizes that true ethical virtues and an ideal society are attainable in this world, through mutual assistance among people. He stresses that society must be governed according to just laws agreed upon by its members, with compliance by all. Any violations of the law or injustice should be punished. Moreover, if a ruler himself acts unjustly, the people have the right to resist, and such resistance should be supported by society. Ibn Sina’s ethical ideas particularly highlight essential moral qualities in daily life, such as humility, respect, courage, honesty, and sincerity [11].

Abu Rayhan Beruni also discussed honesty and falsehood in his writings. He noted that lies arise from ill intentions or anger, and sometimes people spread false information either to please those they favor or to harm those they dislike. Others lie due to a lowly disposition, seeking personal gain or avoiding misfortune. Some individuals spread falsehoods out of habit, as if it were their duty. Beruni argues that those who adhere to truthfulness, avoiding lies, should be respected, while habitual liars, even if admired by others, are morally corrupt. He emphasized: “Speak the truth even if it harms you.” Valor, commonly understood as courage on the battlefield or avoidance of danger, is a form of moral excellence, but the highest form is the ability to speak the truth or act rightly without fear of death. Truthfulness is innately valued and desired by all, but those who have not experienced its sweetness or refuse it do not love it. Therefore, lying diverts a person from justice and leads to other vices such as oppression, false testimony, betrayal of trust, theft, and acts that harm society [12].

Abu Nasr al-Farabi, in his works, spoke about the ideal, complete human being and interpreted the concept of ethics in a broad sense. He emphasized that all people, regardless of religion, belief, race, or language, should strive for harmony and cooperation. He envisioned forming a single, unified human community in the world, where the interests of all citizens are equally considered and acted upon. Al-Farabi, describing the model of an enlightened and morally mature person, wrote: *“Whoever seeks to study wisdom should begin from youth, be physically healthy, possess good morals and etiquette, be truthful in speech, refrain from evil deeds, know all*

laws and regulations, respect the learned and eloquent, generously support knowledge and scholars, and acquire knowledge of all tangible things in the world." [13]

From this, it is clear that al-Farabi paid particular attention to the intellectual and moral education of youth. In his view, knowledge and enlightenment must always be complemented by good ethics; without them, the intended goal of cultivating a fully developed individual cannot be achieved. Scholars such as al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, al-Biruni, and Yusuf Khass Khajib approached ethical issues with a profound philosophical, religious, and social perspective. One notable aspect is that they considered ethics not merely as personal cultivation but in connection with the development of the entire society. For instance, al-Farabi combined ethical excellence with governance through his concept of the "virtuous city," illustrating that moral development and state administration are inseparably linked—a principle that remains relevant for contemporary governance.

Another key point is their integration of ethics with knowledge. Ibn Sina and al-Biruni not only wrote about moral virtues but explained them using scientific reasoning, linking them to human health, intellectual clarity, and societal justice. Their approach aligns closely with modern scientific-ethical principles. A third aspect is found in Yusuf Khass Khajib's *Qutadghu Bilig*, where ethical standards play a central role in the relationships among rulers, advisors, and the populace. This highlights the continued importance of values such as responsibility, justice, and patience in social governance today. Overall, the ethical views of these thinkers represent a harmonious synthesis of scientific thought, Eastern wisdom, Turkic philosophical traditions, and contemporary pedagogical ideas. Their legacy is not only historically significant but also serves as a foundational component of modern education and moral formation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The ethical heritage of Central Asian thinkers from the 9th–12th centuries provides a solid foundation for cultivating values such as moral integrity, patriotism, honesty, knowledge-seeking, and justice among today's youth in Uzbekistan. Their works, when deeply applied within the education system, are crucial for fostering a morally enlightened society. Scholars such as Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan al-Beruni, and Yusuf Khass Khajib approached ethical issues in direct connection with societal development, scientific inquiry, human perfection, state governance, and moral education. In their works, ethics was not merely a matter of individual morality or personal conduct, but was regarded as a fundamental foundation for political, social, and spiritual development within society. The following key conclusions can be drawn from their contributions:

- **Al-Farabi** promoted the idea of the "virtuous person" and the concept of the virtuous state as the basis for establishing an ethical society;
- **Ibn Sina** linked ethics to personal discipline and human health, analyzing it on philosophical and medical grounds;
- **Al-Beruni** emphasized scientific integrity and truthfulness as essential ethical values;
- **Yusuf Khass Khajib** connected ethical principles to state governance, justice, leadership responsibilities, and provided practical guidance for rulers.

In summary, these thinkers constitute a vital part of the heritage of Central Asian ethical thought. Their ideas were relevant not only in their own time but remain highly significant today, especially in the context of building a "New Uzbekistan." They provide guidance for reforming the moral and spiritual sphere, nurturing young generations, promoting ethical maturity in society,

and integrating national values into the education system. Therefore, a deep study, dissemination, and practical implementation of their rich ethical legacy is considered not only a scholarly task but also a crucial moral and educational duty.

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